

EXAMINING THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE CORONAVIRUS (COVID-19) DISEASE ON DROPOUT

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Abstract

This research aims to reveal the effects of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) disease on primary school dropouts by identifying teachers' and administrators' opinions. The new Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) is a virus that was first identified on January 13, 2020, as a result of research conducted on a group of patients who developed respiratory disease symptoms such as fever, cough, and shortness of breath in Wuhan, China. On the other hand, school dropout, as defined in the literature, can be identified as taking a break from school, leaving the institution, and/or leaving the education system. The research was designed in the type of a phenomenology study, one of the qualitative research methods. The study group consists of eight administrators and teachers working in different primary schools in the Anatolian region of Turkey in the Spring academic term of 2021-2022. Data was acquired by a semi-structured interview technique. In the study, the effect of the Covid-19 process on student dropouts and the measures that can be taken were both investigated. It has been concluded that the Covid-19 period does

not have a direct effect on student dropout and that effective information support to students can be a solution to the problems that lead students to drop out of school.

Keywords: primary school, dropout, Coronavirus (COVID-19) disease, phenomenology

Introduction

The increasing importance of primary education in economic development, and the individual rate of return to school, which is a constitutional right today, has brought the need to monitor primary education (Primary and Secondary School) all over the world, especially in developed countries and in our own country as well. Along with many problems such as lack of buildings and equipment in primary education, lack of financing, and qualified teacher shortage; it is the problem of school dropouts that should be seriously addressed. There are three types of school dropouts defined in the literature as; school break, leaving the institution, and leaving the system. Students who take a break usually return after a short while. Those who leave the institution can transfer to another school, and those who leave the system drop out completely for various reasons (Chen, 2008). School dropouts can be optional or compulsory. Voluntary dropout may be due to reasons such as boredom with the program, feeling inadequate, and not liking friends or lessons. Compulsory dropout may be due to failure in the course, a different job opportunity, family problems, financial difficulties, adjustment problems, or a serious illness. When two reasons are compared, voluntary abandonment is less common. The reasons for compulsory dropout are usually external and beyond the control of the student (Bennett, 2003).

The newly discovered Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) is a virus that was first identified on January 13, 2020, as a result of research conducted on a group of

patients who developed respiratory disease symptoms such as fever, cough, and shortness of breath in Wuhan, China. The outbreak was initially detected in seafood and animal market products in the region. Later, it spread from one person to another. The pandemic spread in other cities in Hubei province, especially in Wuhan and other provinces of the People's Republic of China, and then it spread to other countries around the world.

Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses that can cause illness in animals or humans. In humans, several coronaviruses are known to cause respiratory infections, from the common cold to more severe diseases such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). The novel Coronavirus Disease is caused by the SAR-CoV-2 virus. Its most common symptoms are fever, cough, and shortness of breath, and in severe cases pneumonia, severe respiratory failure, and kidney failure, which can lead to death sometimes. Individuals who tested positive for Coronavirus can spread the virus through droplets coming from coughing and sneezing. Surfaces contaminated with these droplets lead to the spread of the disease.

The principles recommended for reducing the overall risk of transmission of acute respiratory infections also apply to the novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19). Attention should be paid to hand cleaning. Hands should be washed with soap and water for at least 20 seconds. Alcohol-based hand antiseptics should be used in cases where soap and water are not available. Healthy individuals should avoid contact with sick people (stay at least 1 m away if possible). If possible during coughing or sneezing, the nose and mouth should be covered with disposable tissue paper. Crowded places should not be entered, if it is necessary to enter, the mouth and nose should be covered and a mask should be used.

The novel Coronavirus Disease is a common problem shared by many primary education systems in many countries. This problem has relevant economic implications for all stakeholders of primary education, especially considering the societal and individual costs. For this reason, it must be necessary to have more detailed information about how the new Coronavirus disease affects student dropout decisions individually and organizationally. In this direction, there are studies examining school dropouts at different levels. Studies on primary school dropouts have mostly focused on financial factors such as students' family structure, background characteristics, educational goals, and pre-school preparation processes.

In the foreign literature, it is seen that the recent studies on school dropouts are concentrated at the higher education level. (Albuquerque, 2008; Araque, Roldán, & Salguero, 2009; Belloc, Maruotti, & Petrella, 2010; Di Pietro & Cutillo, 2007; Gury, 2011; Hovdhaugen, 2009; Lassibille & Gómez, 2008). In Turkey, there are some studies conducted at the level of primary education (Gökşen, Cemalcılar, & Gürlesel, 2006; Özbaş, 2010; Şirin, Özdemir, & Sezgin, 2009), secondary education (Pehlivan, 2006; Şahin & Uysal, 2007, Uysal & Şahin, 2007) and higher education (Bülbül, 2012). Studies that are conducted in Turkey are studies aiming to reveal what school dropout is and its causes. There is no direct research in Turkey that aims to determine the effects of the novel Coronavirus Disease on primary school dropouts and to put forward recommendations for the prevention of school dropouts. This research is important in terms of providing sufficient information about the effect of the novel Coronavirus Disease on school dropout and revealing the measures to be used in minimizing the dropout in primary education.

For this purpose, does the new Coronavirus Disease contribute to primary school dropout? If any, what is the level of this contribution? Also, the purpose of this research is to provide suggestions to prevent the contribution of the new Coronavirus Disease to school dropouts by investigating teachers' and administrators' opinions.

This research was organized in the qualitative research method and phenomenology pattern. Phenomenology research in primary school is defined as focusing on phenomena that are aware of but do not have an in-depth and detailed understanding (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011). The study group of this research consisted of eight administrators and teachers, who worked in a secondary and a primary school in Konya province, Kayseri, Aksaray, and Karaman all located in the central Anatolian region during the 2021-2022 academic year. While determining the research study group, the cross-section sampling technique, one of the purposeful sampling methods, was used. Equal numbers of interviewees were selected from the provinces in the Central Anatolian region. Four of the teachers in the study group were female and four were male. A semi-structured interview form was developed to collect data from the administrators and teachers. In the creation of the semi-structured interview forms, it was first requested to report whether the new Coronavirus Disease contributed to school dropout and, if so, the measures that could be taken to prevent this contribution. The prepared form was presented to the faculty members who have expertise and experience on the subject, and the interview questions were finalized based on their feedback. During the data collection process, the opinions of the administrators and teachers who constituted the study group were received by phone call and written email. In this process, the role of the researcher was to collect data and analyze and interpret the finding. The obtained data in the research were analyzed by the content analysis technique. Content analysis is

carried out when the research cannot be expressed very clearly theoretically or when more in-depth analysis is needed (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011). In the analysis of the data, first of all, the data were placed under themes and sub-themes obtained through coding. As the last step, the themes and sub-themes obtained were presented to the opinion of an expert in educational sciences and qualitative research, and inter-coder reliability analysis was performed on the themes obtained. Inter-coder reliability = [Agreement / (Agreement + Disagreement)] X 100 formula was used and the percentage of intercoder reliability was calculated as 87%(Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Results

The findings were presented, supported by direct quotations from the teachers' views, within the scope of the purpose of the research.

Contribution of the new coronavirus disease process to school dropout.

In the study, firstly, teachers were asked about their thoughts on whether the new Coronavirus Disease contributed to school dropouts. Teachers' views on this subject were grouped under two sub-themes; "happened or did not happen". These themes are included in Table 1.

Theme	Sub-theme	Konya		Kayseri		Aksaray		Karaman	
The New Coronavirus Disease	has contributed to school dropout	Adm in	Lecturer	Adm in	Lecturer	Adm in	Lecturer	Adm in	lecturer.
		1							
	has not contributed to	1		1	1	1	1	1	1

	school dropout				
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Table1. *Teachers' Opinions on the Contribution of the New Coronavirus Disease Process to School dropouts*

When the opinions were examined, most of the administrators and teachers stated that the new Coronavirus Disease period did not contribute to school dropouts. One teacher stated that the Coronavirus period contributed to school dropouts

Yes, as in every field, the negative effect of covid was reflected on the school and students. School dropouts were seen more frequently in students compared to other times. One of our students, who did not want to be sick and especially did not want to infect his old grandfather, who was at home, dropped out of school (secondary school assistant principal, Konya).

In our school, Covid 19 did not have an impact on students' dropouts. None of the students I took classes with dropped out of school since, during this process, distance education opportunities were recognized. (secondary school teacher, Aksaray)

The reasons for the contribution of the new Coronavirus disease period to school dropout

In line with the teachers' view, which is seen in table 1 as the reason for the dropout during the period of Coronavirus, the fear of the student being sick and the fear of infecting his grandfather who is especially in the risk group over 60, is seen as the reason why the student had dropped out of school. Eight of the teachers stated that Coronavirus did not contribute to school dropouts. They explained their answers by stating that distance learning environments were created in their schools. Also, the school environment was prepared in accordance with the hygiene rules and awareness was raised about the recent Coronavirus Disease. All four teachers stated that four of their students were enrolled in an open secondary school.

Last year, distance education was conducted at our school. During this period, classrooms were prepared in accordance with hygiene rules. Students were stuck wearing masks. The effect of the disease was minimized. (Primary school teacher, Kayseri).

In our school, Covid 19 did not have an impact on students' dropouts. However, two of our students were enrolled in open secondary school. Five of my students asked me for information about moving to an open secondary school. However, they haven't applied to an open education school yet. (Primary School Teacher, Konya)

Seven or eight of my students asked me for some information about moving to open secondary school. No one left school. (primary school principal, Karaman)

Recommendations to prevent the contribution of the New Coronavirus Disease process to school dropout

According to the observations of the teachers who participated in our research, the majority of the opinions is that the Coronavirus Disease period does not directly contribute to school dropouts. To prevent school dropouts, suggestions have been made. Taking general health measures against Coronavirus Disease and applying these measures will seriously lay the groundwork for school attendance.

Our Ministry has received articles regarding the measures that should be taken into consideration during the Coronavirus Disease period. Taking the precautions into consideration, and applying it will seriously ensure safety in terms of health. As long as the rules are followed. (Middle School Principal, Kayseri).

Mask usage, cleaning, and communication at appropriate intervals will be appropriate. Distance learning can also be put back into service if needed. The content of distance education materials can be developed. (Secondary school teacher, Karaman)

In our school, information is given periodically about the negative effects of Covid 19. (Primary school principal, Aksaray)

These results are according to the observations of the teachers participating in our research. The Coronavirus Disease period does not directly contribute to school dropouts. There may be an indirect effect as well as other social, economic, and cultural reasons for early leaving. Suggestions made in studies conducted at primary education (Gökşen, Cemalcılar, & Gürlesel, 2006; Özbaş, 2010; Şirin, Özdemir, & Sezgin, 2009) and secondary education (Pehlivan, 2006; Şahin & Uysal, 2007, Uysal & Şahin, 2007) level school dropouts is gaining importance.

To minimize the indirect effect of the Coronavirus Disease on school dropouts and to provide education in a healthy environment, positive contributions and implementation of the practices are recommended by the Ministry of National Education and Health without interruption.

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